

Survival Prediction in Heart Failure using Machine Learning Algorithms.

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Received: 25-06-2022 / Revised: 25-07-2022 / Accepted: 15-08-2022

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Background: Heart failure is the final stage of various cardiovascular diseases. Statistical models and machine learning (ML) algorithms have been proposed to predict heart failure. However, the present study used ML classifiers to predict survival in heart failure patients.

Materials and Methods: The study dataset consists of a random sample of medical records of 299 heart failure patients. The dataset is publicly available on the Machine Learning Repository website of the University of California Irvine (UCI ML). Thirteen predictors and one response variable ('Event') were present in the database. Except for 'Time', other predictors were used in predicting survival in heart failure patients. Oversampling methods were employed to balance the dataset using the ROSE package in R. Predictors differed and contributed significantly to prediction and were used to train ML classifiers on MATLAB classifier application with 5-fold cross-validation. The performance metrics of the machine learning classifier were expressed as accuracy, the area under the receiver operator characteristic (AU-ROC) curve, sensitivity, and specificity.

Results: The predictors used to train machine learning classifiers were hypertension, age, creatinine concentration, CPK, ejection fraction, and sodium concentration. The best model was the ensemble-based Subspace K-nearest neighbor model. The accuracy, AU-ROC, sensitivity, and specificity were 89.5%, 93%, 87%, and 92%, respectively.

Conclusion: The present study used biostatistical tests and a logistic regression model to optimize feature selection. The features that contributed significantly to the logistic regression model were used to train machine learning classifiers. The study showed better performance metrics in predicting survival in heart failure patients.

Keywords: classifiers, ejection fraction, heart failure, machine learning, prediction.

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Introduction

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are the leading cause of mortality worldwide, with an estimated 17.9 million deaths yearly. CVDs are a group of heart and blood vessel disorders, including coronary heart disease, cerebrovascular disease, rheumatic heart disease, and other conditions. [1] Heart failure (HF) is a clinical syndrome characterized by shortness of breath, fatigue, and signs of edema and pulmonary crackles. [2] Heart failure is a risk factor for diseases such as atrial fibrillation, stroke, and coronary artery disease. Further, heart failure is a consequence of other diseases, including rheumatic, hypertensive, or coronary artery disease. [3] Ischemic heart disease is the leading cause of mortality. Global Burden of Disease (GBD) Study 2019 ranked risk factors for ischemic heart disease including high systolic blood pressure, dietary risks, high LDL cholesterol, air pollution, high body mass index, tobacco, high plasma blood glucose, kidney dysfunction, non-optimal temperature, other environmental risks, alcohol use, and low physical activity. [4] Heart failure is characterized by inadequate pumping of blood by the heart. Approximately one-half of the patients with heart failure have preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF) rather than reduced ejection fraction (HFrEF). [5] Statistical and machine learning models were used to predict disease models in medicine. [6,7,8,9,10,11,12] Many models predict heart failure using various risk factors. [13,14] However, the present study predicts the survival of heart failure patients using machine learning classification.

Materials and Methods

The present study predicts survival in heart failure patients using machine learning (ML) classifiers. The study dataset consists of a random sample of medical records of 299 heart failure patients collected at the Faisalabad Institute of Cardiology and the Allied Hospital in

Faisalabad (Punjab, Pakistan) during April–December 2015. The dataset is publicly available on the Machine Learning Repository website of the University of California Irvine (UCI ML). Thirteen predictors and one response variable ('Event') were present in the database. Except for 'Time', other predictors were used in predicting survival in heart failure patients. The predictors included were gender, smoking, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, anemia, age, ejection fraction, serum creatinine, sodium concentration, platelets, and creatine phosphate kinase concentration. The response variable 'Event' has two levels: death (N= 203) and alive (N= 96). As the dataset was imbalanced, oversampling methods were employed using the ROSE package in R. The balanced data has 197 alive and 203 death cases. The features differed significantly between the two response levels using biostatistical tests. A logistic regression model using the stepwise method was fitted using significantly differed features to find the contribution of each predictor in survival prediction. The features contributing significantly were chosen for ML training and classification. The ML classifier application on MATLAB 2019a was used for classification with 5-fold cross-validation.

The classifiers used in this application include Decision Trees, Support Vector Machine (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and ensemble learning classifiers. The decision trees include complex, medium, and simple tree classifiers. Similarly, the SVMs include linear, quadratic, cubic, fine Gaussian, medium Gaussian, and coarse Gaussian classifiers. The ensemble classifiers have boosted trees, bagged trees, and RUS boosted tree classifiers.

Statistical analysis

The quantitative data were expressed in median (IQR) and compared using the

non-parametric Mann-Whitney's U test. The categorical data were expressed in percentage, and the relationship between discrete variables was found using a chi-squared test. The performance metrics of the machine learning classifier were expressed as accuracy, the area under the receiver operator characteristic (AU-ROC) curve, sensitivity, and specificity. R version 4.1.2 software was used for balancing data between two groups, and JASP version 0.16.2 was used for statistical analysis. MATLAB Classification Learner application 2019a

was used for training and prediction. The significance level was considered at 5%.

Results

The discrete variables including gender [$\chi^2 = 0.175, p = 0.676$], smoking [$\chi^2 = 0.044, p = 0.833$], diabetes mellitus [$\chi^2 = 0.023, p = 0.878$], anemia [$\chi^2 = 0.21, p = 0.647$] did not differ significantly except hypertension [$\chi^2 = 10.913, p < 0.001$] between the two groups of heart failure. The patients who died due to heart failure had a higher percentage of hypertensives than alive patients.

Table 1: Comparison of discrete features in dead and alive patients of heart failure.

Category	Levels	Alive	Death	χ^2 value	p-value
Gender	Female	71(34.975)	65(32.995)	0.175	0.676
	Male	132(65.025)	132(67.005)		
Smoking	Non-smoker	137(67.488)	131(66.497)	0.044	0.833
	Smoker	66(32.512)	66(33.503)		
Diabetes Mellitus	Absent	118(58.128)	116(58.883)	0.023	0.878
	Present	85(41.872)	81(41.117)		
Hypertension	Absent	137(67.488)	101(51.269)	10.913	< .001
	Present	66(32.512)	96(48.731)		
Anemia	Absent	120(59.113)	112(56.853)	0.21	0.647
	Present	83(40.887)	85(43.147)		

In case of continuous variables, the patients died of heart failure showed higher age [$W=15415, p < 0.001$], creatinine levels [$W= 11481, p < 0.001$], and creatine phosphate kinase concentration [$W=17609.5, p = 0.038$]. However, the same patients had a lower

levels of ejection fraction [$W= 28476, p < 0.001$], and sodium concentration [$W=25622.5, p < 0.001$] compared to alive patients. However, platelets showed no significant differences between the two groups [$W = 21337, p = 0.246$].

Table 2: Comparison of continuous features in dead and alive patients of heart failure

		Median	IQR*	W	p-value
Age	Alive	60	15	15415	< .001
	Death	65	22		
Ejection fraction	Alive	38	10	28476	< .001
	Death	30	18		
Sodium	Alive	137	4.5	25622.5	< .001
	Death	136	5		
Creatinine	Alive	1	0.3	11481	< .001
	Death	1.3	0.83		
Platelets	Alive	263000	82500	21337	0.246
	Death	255000	122000		
CPK	Alive	245	473	17609.5	0.038
	Death	418	439		

*IQR: Interquartile range; W: test statistics

The variables significantly differed between the two groups, including hypertension, age, creatinine concentration, CPK, ejection fraction, and sodium concentration, were selected to fit a logistic regression model using the stepwise method. The model showed that all the variables contributed significantly to the prediction of the heart failure group.

Table 3: Estimated parameters of the Logistic regression model using predictors with response variable as survival in heart failure patients.

Parameter	Estimate	Standard Error	z	Wald Test		
				Wald Statistic	df*	p-value
(Intercept)	8.89	3.791	2.345	5.5	1	0.019
Ejection.Fraction	-0.063	0.011	-5.723	32.758	1	< .001
Serum creatinine	0.609	0.163	3.733	13.938	1	< .001
Age	0.048	0.01	4.617	21.321	1	< .001
CPK	0	0	3.002	9.01	1	0.003
Blood pressure	0.761	0.242	3.147	9.903	1	0.002
Serum sodium	-0.081	0.028	-2.898	8.397	1	0.004

*df: degrees of freedom

Table 4: Performance metrics of the ensemble-based Subspace KNN model used for predicting survival in heart failure patients.

Performance metrics	Percentage
Accuracy	89.5%
AUC	93%
Sensitivity	87%
Specificity	92%

The variables mentioned above were used as predictors to train various Machine learning classifiers using the Classification learner app on MATLAB. The best model was the ensemble-based Subspace K-nearest neighbor model. The accuracy, AU-ROC, sensitivity, and specificity were 89.5%, 93%, 87%, and 92%, respectively.

Figure 1: Confusion matrix for the ensemble-based Subspace KNN model.

Figure 2: The area under the receiver operator characteristic curve for the ensemble-based Subspace KNN model.

Discussion

Heart failure is a clinical syndrome seen in the terminal stage of many heart diseases. The heart's reduced pumping ability leads to the inadequate blood supply to the body. [2] However, nearly half of the patients with heart failure have preserved ejection fraction. [6] The present study generates results that differ from the original dataset curators study. The present study used more predictors to increase performance metrics. Ahmad et al. did a survival analysis of heart failure patients using the same dataset. Cox regression was used to model the mortality. Researchers found age, renal dysfunction, blood pressure, ejection fraction, and anemia were significant risk factors governing the mortality risk. [15] The present study used an ensemble-based Subspace K-nearest neighbor model with accuracy, AU-ROC, sensitivity, and specificity were 89.5%, 93%, 87%, and 92%, respectively.

Many studies were focused on the prediction of heart failure. [16,17,18] However, fewer studies focused on the prediction of adverse outcomes in heart failure patients. The present study used

machine learning classifiers to predict survival in heart failure patients.

Smith et al., with an echocardiogram of 4696 patients, developed a risk model to predict the 5-year mortality risk or hospitalization in heart failure patients from 1999 to 2004. Researchers observed a 56% five-year risk of hospitalization for heart failure or death (95% confidence interval, 54% to 58%). The hazard ratios for echocardiogram data contributed statistically significantly to the model. However, echocardiogram findings did not improve prediction risk once demographic and clinical data were used. [19] Chicco et al. predict the survival of heart failure patients using machine learning algorithms. They develop a two-feature model using ejection fraction and serum creatinine. The Random Forest performed best in the survival prediction, obtaining an accuracy of 74% and AU-ROC of 80%. [20]. Newaj et al. used a Random Forest classifier to predict survival on the same dataset. Researchers found a maximum G-mean score of 76.83% with a sensitivity score of 80.21%. [21] Zeman et al. used two unsupervised models (K-Means and Fuzzy C-Means clustering) and three

supervised classifiers (Random Forest, XGBoost, and Decision Tree) to demonstrate a superior performance of the supervised ML algorithms over unsupervised models. The proposed supervised stacked ensemble learning model can achieve an accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score of 99.98%. [22] The performance metrics might depend on the number of independent predictors used to train ML classifiers. The present study used six predictors, including hypertension, age, serum creatinine, CPK, ejection fraction, and serum sodium concentration, to train machine learning classifiers. [23]

Conclusion

The present study used biostatistical and logistic regression models to optimize feature selection. The features that contributed significantly to the logistic regression model were used to train machine learning classifiers. The study showed better performance metrics in predicting survival in heart failure patients.

Research Quality and Ethics Statement-

The present study with report quality, formatting, and reproducibility guidelines set forth by the EQUATOR Network. The data used was acquired from the UCL repository, so exempted from an Institutional Review Board / Ethics Committee review.

Conflicts of interest: Nil

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